

WETTABILITY OF MOLTEN Fe-Si-B ALLOY ON GRAPHITE, Al₂O₃, AND h-BN SUBSTRATES

Jian Meng Jiao*, Bettina Grorud, Jafar Safarian, Merete Tangstad

Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Norwegian University of Science and
Technology (NTNU), Alfred Getz' vei 2, Trondheim, 7491, Norway

Keywords: wettability, phase change material, graphite, silicon carbide, hexagonal boron nitride.

Abstract

Fe-26.38Si-9.35B alloy (numbers in mass %) is of interest as a phase change material (PCM) because it exhibits high thermal conductivity, moderate melting point, high latent heat, and low cost. This study offers valuable insights into the contact angles of molten eutectic Fe-26.38Si-9.35B alloy on various substrates using the sessile drop method. Moreover, the reactivity has been investigated by examining the cross-sections between Fe-26.38Si-9.35B droplets and substrates with a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The purpose of this study is to find a proper refractory material for the new Fe-26.38Si-9.35B PCM. These wetting tests confirm that the contact angle between molten Fe-26.38Si-9.35B and Al₂O₃ is about 112°. Molten Fe-26.38Si-9.35B spreads over the graphite plate and the contact angle is estimated to be 31° and a continuous silicon carbide (SiC) layer is formed between the molten Fe-26.38Si-9.35B and graphite. Interestingly, three melting/solidification cycles have been performed on hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN) substrate at the temperature range of 1100-1550 °C. The contact angle is observed to be 142° in the first cycle, 105° in the second cycle, and 130° in the third cycle. This study contributes to our understanding of the wettability properties of molten Fe-26.38Si-9.35B alloy on various substrates.

Introduction

The high demand to seek renewable and clean energy that can substitute fossil fuels has become a vital role in the development of our society. However, the mismatch between the renewable energy supply and electricity demand has become one of the main obstacles for future renewable energy sources. Therefore, there has been renewed interest in phase change material (PCM) because it offers high energy storage density and isothermal behavior during the phase transformation [1]. However, few studies have been investigated PCMs with high-temperature energy storage beyond 1000 °C. In 2014, pure silicon was chosen as a PCM to develop a solar thermal propulsion system for micro-satellites due to its extremely high fusion latent heat (1800 J/g) and high melting point (1414 °C) [2]. Nevertheless, the considerable silicon volume expansion resulted in the breakage of PCM container [3]. Later, a novel Si-3.25B PCM was proposed by Datas *et al.* [4] as the lattice contraction of the silicon and boron alloy [5]. Extensively experiments were done researching the Si-3.25B eutectic alloy in graphite crucibles [6]. It is found that the volume expansion of the new Si-3.25B PCM is similar with pure silicon, and it has severe chemical corrosion with the graphite at high temperatures. In this regard, a eutectic Fe-26.38Si-9.35B alloy was first chosen to be a new PCM instead of Si-3.25B eutectic alloy. The thermodynamic properties of Fe-Si-B ternary alloy were investigated systematically by FactSage [6]. The high latent heat (1250 kWh/m³) at its

melting temperature (1157 °C) is regarded as a desirable PCM in the latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) system.

In view of the application of Fe-26.38Si-9.35B alloy, the high reactivity of molten Fe-26.38Si-9.35B with refractory materials may cause the damage of PCM containers. Hence, the wettability of molten Fe-26.38Si-9.35B in contact with ceramic substrates plays a critical role in the fields of high-temperature PCM containers. The purpose of this study is to investigate the wettability properties of molten Fe-26.38Si-9.35B in contact with graphite, Al₂O₃, and h-BN substrates, with a particular emphasis on the effects of the interlayer formation between Fe-26.38Si-9.35B droplet and different ceramic substrates.

Experimental Procedure

Materials and Apparatus

The Fe-26.38Si-9.35B master alloy was produced in an induction furnace. The chemical composition of the eutectic Fe-26.38Si-9.35B master alloy was analyzed by ICP-MS. Both the detected and normalized content of silicon, iron, boron, aluminum, and manganese, in addition to the ideal composition of the alloy, are given in Table I. The experiments were performed on wetting of Fe-26.38Si-9.35B on 99.7% Al₂O₃, graphite (ISO-88), and 99.8% h-BN.

The sessile drop furnace was designed to observe the behavior of the sample on substrate at high temperature. It is possible to measure the wetting angle of a sessile drop, observe the softening and melting point of substances and investigate the reactivity between various materials. All the heated furnace parts, including the element and heat shields, are constructed of graphite, allowing both extremely fast and slow heating in an inert and reduction atmosphere. A digital video camera (Sony XCD-SX910CR) is used to record the shape of the droplet [7].

Table I Chemical composition of the Fe-Si-B master alloy analyzed by ICP-MS. [mass %]

Sample		Si	Fe	B	Al	Mn
Fe-Si-B	Detected	26.68	56.47	8.11	0.067	0.21
	Normalized	29.15	61.69	8.86	0.073	0.23
	Ideal composition	26.38	64.27	9.35		

Experimental Design

The Fe-26.38Si-9.35B master alloy was etched in an HF, HNO₃, and ethanol (1:5:2) solution bath in 10 s, rinsed with water and ethanol and contained in ethanol before the wetting experiments, to dissolve any oxide layer. After that, a small piece of master alloy was chosen and placed on the top of the substrate. Heating was performed in a vacuum of 10⁻¹ mbar to 1100 °C in 4 min, and then, the temperature was raised to the set temperature at a low rate. The sample was cooled down to the room temperature with a natural cooling rate after the experiments.

Figure 1a-b presents the temperature profile with different substrates. The heating process is the same on graphite and Al₂O₃ substrates, as shown in Figure 1a. It is seen from the figure that the temperature was raised to 1550 °C with a rate of 10 °C/min after 1100 °C. If we turn to the temperature profile on h-BN substrate, the difference between h-BN and graphite was that three thermal cycles were done in the heating process. Figure 1b shows a gradual increase in the temperature up to 1350 °C with a heating rate of 5 °C/min, then, 10 °C/min from 1350 °C to 1550

°C, after that, cooled to 1100 °C, following with a rate of 10 °C/min to 1550 °C again. The cycle was done three times.

Figure 1. Temperature profile of the Fe-Si-B particle in the wetting experiments. a) graphite and Al₂O₃, b) Si₃N₄, c) BN.

When the Fe-Si-B particle completely melts, the contact is maintained by its intermolecular interaction between the Fe-Si-B drop and its substrate, which is referred to as wetting. Additionally, the wetting is characterized by the contact angle, θ . Presently, the contact angle of Fe-Si-B drop on the substrate is defined in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Contact angle θ of Fe-Si-B drop resting on the substrate.

The Fe-26.38Si-9.35B samples were cut perpendicular to the interface. After polishing, the scanning electron microscope (SEM) supplied with energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) technique was used to investigate the microstructures. It should be noted that the samples were carbon sputtered prior to analysis.

Results and Discussion

Wettability Property of Fe-26.38Si-9.35B Alloy on Graphite Substrate

Figure 3 is a series of images which shows the Fe-26.38Si-9.35B particle placed on graphite substrate under vacuum. When the temperature reached to 1220 °C, the sample started to melt, as shown in the white dotted circle in Figure 5. This temperature is higher than the theoretical melting point of 1157 °C [6], possibly due to a short etching time leading to the oxide layer still existed on

the interface of the Fe-26.38Si-9.35B particle. The complete melting was reached at a temperature of 1350 °C.

Figure 3. Images of Fe-26.38Si-9.35B alloy droplets on the graphite substrate.

As shown in Figure 4 (grey line), the contact angle on graphite decreased from an initial value of $90 \pm 5^\circ$ at 1350 °C to $31 \pm 1^\circ$ at 1550 °C. It is worth to be noted that the time $t = 0$ corresponds to complete melting of Fe-26.38Si-9.35B. As expected for the reactive Fe-26.38Si-9.35B /graphite system, a continuous SiC layer was detected by EDS analysis at the interface after cooling to room temperature (Figure 5).

It is apparent from Figure 4 that the contact angle decreases first rapidly and then slowly, and tends towards its equilibrium value. In the beginning, the wetting angle of $90 \pm 5^\circ$ shows a non-wetting between molten Fe-26.38Si-9.35B and graphite. With the time increasing in the heating process, silicon penetrated to the graphite substrate leading to a SiC layer formed between the molten Fe-26.38Si-9.35B and graphite, along with the decrease of contact angle. Hence, the contact angle is changed to the angle between the reacted substrate (SiC) and molten Fe-26.38Si-9.35B. Later, the spread of the molten Fe-26.38Si-9.35B is hindered by the local chemical process at the triple line. Therefore, the equilibrium contact angle is close to 31° on SiC substrate from graphite.

The contact angle of Fe-5.3Si-3B alloy on SiC substrate was measured by Cao *et al.* [8] under vacuum. The contact angle of 100° on SiC substrate at equilibrium state was much higher than our experimental results. Moreover, considerable literatures have shown that the contact angle of pure iron in contact with graphite was at the range of $0-66^\circ$ under different atmosphere [9–12]. Rubio *et al.* [13] also found that the contact angle of Fe-14.1Si droplet was 38° at 1550 °C, which was close to our experimental results. It should be noted that the wetting was highly affected by the carbon content in the melt, in which the contact angle increased up to about 140° [10].

Figure 4. Contact angle as a function of time for molten Fe-26.38Si-9.35B on graphite and Al₂O₃ substrates at the temperature range of 1350-1550 °C.

Figure 5. The interface between Fe-26.38Si-9.35B droplet and graphite substrate.

Wettability Property of Fe-26.38Si-9.35B Alloy on Al₂O₃ Substrate

Figure 6 shows the behavior of Fe-26.38Si-9.35B particle as it melts on Al₂O₃. The Fe-26.38Si-9.35B particle started to melt at 1219 °C and it appeared complete molten at 1354 °C. It agrees well with the melting process on graphite.

Figure 4 shows the contact angle as a function of time for molten Fe-26.38Si-9.35B on Al₂O₃ at the temperature range of 1354-1550 °C. The time $t = 0$ represents the complete melting of Fe-26.38Si-9.35B on Al₂O₃. It can be seen from the figure that the contact angle increases from 98° at 1354 °C to 112° at 1550 °C. Comparing the contact angle of Fe-5.3Si-3B alloy on Al₂O₃ measured by Cao *et al.* [8], the angle of 116° was consistent with our experimental results.

As soon as the droplet was molten, a strong vibration was observed at the temperature range of 1470-1550 °C, accompanied by some small Fe-26.38Si-9.35B droplets formed on the left side (as shown in Figure 6 at 1550 °C and Figure 7a). The corrosion surface in Figure 7a was observed after the wetting test. It may be caused by the reaction between silicon and the dissolved oxygen from Al₂O₃ with the formation of volatile SiO at the triple line. Simultaneously, the SiO gas would recede the triple line and increase the contact angle (as shown in Figure 4). This phenomenon is particularly pronounced during vacuum [14].

The interface characterization in the Fe-26.38Si-9.35B/Al₂O₃ system is shown in Figure 7b. A crack line was observed at the interface. Simultaneously, an EDS line scan was done from the Fe-26.38Si-9.35B droplet to Al₂O₃ based on the red line in Figure 7b, and the result is presented in Figure 8. As the sample was carbon sputtered prior to analysis to ensure sufficient conductivity, the detection of carbon is negligible. What is interesting about the result in Figure 8 is that no penetration was detected in the Al₂O₃ side, and approximately 5 at.% oxygen was detected in the Fe-26.38Si-9.35B droplet. The quantitative measurement of oxygen is not very reliable, however, the use of Al₂O₃ as the PCM container will increase the oxygen content in the Fe-26.38Si-9.35B.

Figure 6. Images of Fe-26.38Si-9.35B alloy droplet on the Al₂O₃ substrate.

Figure 7. a) Macroscopic images of the Fe-26.38Si-9.35B droplet/Al₂O₃ after the wetting test. b) The interface between Fe-26.38Si-9.35B droplet and Al₂O₃ substrate.

Figure 8. EDS line scan from Fe-26.38Si-9.35B droplet to Al₂O₃ substrate.

Wettability Property of Fe-26.38Si-9.35B Alloy on h-BN Substrate

Figure 9 provides the images of Fe-26.38Si-9.35B droplet on h-BN with three times melting/solidification process between 1100 °C and 1550 °C. It is seen from the figure that the Fe-26.38Si-9.35B particle started to melt at 1218 °C in the first cycle and 1221 °C in the second cycle. Comparing the melting temperature on graphite and Al₂O₃, it indicates that the Fe-26.38Si-9.35B alloy starts to melt at 1218-1221 °C.

Figure 10 shows the contact angle as a function of temperature for the molten Fe-26.38Si-9.35B on h-BN in the melting/solidification process between 1250 °C and 1550 °C. The contact angle keeps at approximately 142° in the first cycle. In the second cycle, it changed abruptly to 100° at 1468 °C. After a slight increase to 105°, it increased to 130° at 1477 °C in the third cycle.

Cao *et al.* [8] measured the contact angles of molten Fe-5.3Si-3B on h-BN under vacuum, the angle of 140°-147.5° was observed at the temperature of 1160-1360 °C. Moreover, the contact angle of molten silicon on h-BN substrate was measured by Drevet *et al.* [15] lying between 114° and 136° under vacuum. Both of them were in accordance with our experimental results.

Significantly, the formation of Si_3N_4 was found at the interface in the Si/BN and Fe-5.3Si-3B/BN systems, even though the Gibbs energy of the reaction of silicon droplet and h-BN is positive [8,15]. Wojciech *et al.* [16] investigated the wetting behavior of molten silicon with h-BN substrate, and they found that Si_3N_4 was not detected at the interface in the Si/h-BN system, except for SiC phase confirmed by the SEM/EDS examinations, which is an agreement with our microstructure results (Figure 11). Furthermore, they found that Si_3N_4 is decomposed to SiC and N_2 above 1410 °C in the presence of carbon. Hence, SiC may be caused by the presence of Si_3N_4 at the interface. Therefore, the behavior for the Fe-26.38Si-9.35B/h-BN system can be explained. The theory is that a Si_3N_4 layer was formed in the second cycle since the reaction of silicon and h-BN, it leads to the contact angle decrease from 142° to 100°. However, the reactivity between silicon and h-BN is weak. The formed Si_3N_4 layer is not stable, resulting in breaking in the third cycle, accompanied by the contact angle increasing to 130° again. In conclusion, h-BN is a potential material to be used as the PCM container, regardless of the unstable formation of Si_3N_4 layer.

Figure 9. Images of Fe-26.38Si-9.35B alloy droplet on h-BN substrate.

Figure 10. Contact angle as a function of temperature for the molten Fe-26.38Si-9.35B on h-BN substrate in the three times melting/solidification process.

Figure 11. The interface between Fe-26.38Si-9.35B droplet and h-BN substrate.

Conclusions

The wettability of molten Fe-26.38Si-9.35B in contact with graphite, Al_2O_3 , and h-BN substrates was investigated in the sessile drop furnace under vacuum. The main conclusions are as follows:

- 1) The start melting temperature of Fe-26.38Si-9.35B alloy is measured to be at the range of 1218-1221 °C.
- 2) The steady contact angles observed on graphite, Al_2O_3 and h-BN substrates are equal to 31°, 112° and 130° respectively.
- 3) A continuous SiC layer was formed in the Fe-26.38Si-9.35B/graphite system. The spreading kinetics is limited by the local chemical process at the triple line.
- 4) No penetration was detected in the Fe-26.38Si-9.35B/ Al_2O_3 system. Oxygen may however be dissolved into the Fe-26.38Si-9.35B alloy.
- 5) The contact angle is not stable in the Fe-26.38Si-9.35B/h-BN system. However, it does not affect the use of h-BN as the PCM container.

Acknowledgment

The project AMADEUS has received funds from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, FET-OPEN action, under Grant agreement 737054.

Reference

- [1] M. Liu et al., “A eutectic salt high temperature phase change material: Thermal stability and corrosion of SS316 with respect to thermal cycling,” *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, 170 (2017) 1–7.
- [2] R. Matthew et al., High Temperature Latent Heat Thermal Energy Storage To Augment Solar Thermal Propulsion for Microsatellites, (2014).
- [3] W.K. Rhim, K. Ohsaka, “Thermophysical properties measurement of molten silicon by high-temperature electrostatic levitator: Density, volume expansion, specific heat capacity,

- emissivity, surface tension and viscosity,” *J. Cryst. Growth*, 208 (1) (2000) 313–321.
- [4] A. Datas et al., “Ultra high temperature latent heat energy storage and thermophotovoltaic energy conversion,” *Energy*, 107 (2016) 542–549.
- [5] R.W. Olesinski, G.J. Abbaschian, “The B-Si (Boron-Silicon) system,” *Bull. Alloy Phase Diagrams*, 5 (5) (1984) 478–484.
- [6] B. Grorud, “Interaction of Eutectic Fe-Si-B Alloy with Graphite Crucibles,” (Ph.D. thesis, NTNU, 2018), 43-50.
- [7] A. Ciftja et al., “Wetting Properties of Molten Silicon with Graphite Materials,” *Metall. Mater. Trans. A*, 41 (12) (2010) 3183–3195.
- [8] H. Gao et al., “The influence of substrate and atmosphere on the properties of FeSiB(Cu,Nb) alloy melts,” *Sci. China Technol. Sci.*, 59 (12) (2016) 1892–1898.
- [9] M. Humenik, W. Kingery, “Metal-Ceramic Interactions: III, Surface Tension and Wettability of Metal-Ceramic Systems,” *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 37 (1) (1954) 18–23.
- [10] H. Sun et al., “Carbon Solution in Liquid Iron and Iron Alloys,” *High Temp. Mater. Process.*, 17 (4) (1998) 257–270.
- [11] C. Wu, V. Sahajwalla, “Influence of melt carbon and sulfur on the wetting of solid graphite by Fe-C-S melts,” *Metall. Mater. Trans. B Process Metall. Mater. Process. Sci.*, 29 (2) (1998) 471–477.
- [12] L. Zhao, V. Sahajwalla, “Interfacial phenomena during wetting of graphite/alumina mixtures by liquid iron,” *ISIJ Int.*, 43 (1) (2003) 1–6.
- [13] P.J.Y. Rubio et al., “Dynamic Wetting of Graphite and SiC by Ferrosilicon Alloys and Silicon at 1550 C,” *ISIJ Int.*, 46 (11) (2006) 1570–1576.
- [14] B. Drevet, N. Eustathopoulos, Wetting of ceramics by molten silicon and silicon alloys: A review, in: *J. Mater. Sci.*, Springer US, 2012): pp. 8247–8260.
- [15] B. Drevet et al., “Wetting and adhesion of Si on Si₃N₄ and BN substrates,” *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.*, 29 (11) (2009) 2363–2367.
- [16] W. Polkowski et al., “Wetting Behavior and Reactivity of Molten Silicon with h-BN Substrate at Ultrahigh Temperatures up to 1750 °C,” *J. Mater. Eng. Perform.*, (7) (2017) 1–14.